

Activity Measurement with Resin Membrane Electrode. Part II. Determination of Activity-Solubility Products of Sparingly Soluble Salts*

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Synthetic ion-exchange resin membrane electrodes are tested for their good performances in Calcium and Barium ion activity measurements. Activity of Calcium and Barium ions in their sparingly soluble Sulphate, Carbonate and Oxalate salts are determined and their activity solubility products are calculated. Appreciable difference between the solubility product and activity solubility product in the case of calcium sulphate has been observed.

Mac Dougall and Davies¹, Bronsted and La Mer² and others³ measured the solubilities of some sparingly soluble salts in solutions of electrolytes in order to test the validity of the Debye-Hückel activity coefficient expressions. Owen⁴ determined the solubility product of difficultly soluble salt by the use of electrodes reversible with respect to one of the ions of the salt.

In a saturated solution, an equilibrium is established between the solute that is in solution and the solute that remains undissolved. For an electrolyte ML which gives v_i cations of charge z_i and v_j anions of charge z_j , the equilibrium constant between dissolved and undissolved electrolytes, K_s is given by

$$K_s = \frac{a_{M^{z_i}}^{v_i} a_{L^{z_j}}^{v_j}}{a_{ML}} = [M^{z_i}]^{v_i} [L^{z_j}]^{v_j} \gamma_M \gamma_L \quad \dots (1)$$

where the terms have their usual significances. K_s is termed as activity solubility product.

A cation exchange resin membrane (MC-3470 XL) electrode was used to determine the Hydrogen and Sodium ion activities in simple and polyelectrolyte solutions⁵. The same electrode was conditioned for the determination of Calcium and Barium ion activities.

Sulphates, Carbonates and Oxalates of Calcium and Barium were selected for our study. The cation activities of these sparingly soluble salts in saturated solutions were determined from the following cell,

Saturated calomel electrode	Inner solution of known activity	Membrane	Outer solution of sparingly soluble salt (saturated)	Saturated calomel electrode
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* Communicated to the 56th Session of the Indian Science Congress Association—1969.

1. G. Mac Dougall and C. W. Davies, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 1416.
2. J. N. Bronsted and V. K. La Mer, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, **46**, 535.
3. V. K. La Mer and F. H. Goldman, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, **51**, 2632.
4. B. B. Owen, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, **60**, 2229.
5. A. Sarkar, S. C. Ghosh and S. K. Mukherjee. Communicated to the Indian Chemical Society for the 6th Annual Convention, 1968.

using the following equation within the valid range of the resin membrane electrode (as shown in the Table I)

$$E_M = \frac{RT}{ZF} \ln \frac{a_1}{a_2} \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

EXPERIMENTAL

The salts were prepared in the laboratory by the standard method, washed with cold and hot water to remove the trace amount of impurities. Difficulties were encountered in purifying oxalates. The filtrates in each washing were tested to show the absence of impurities by the usual procedure.

The salts were then taken in clean bottles and after adding water the bottles with the contents were warmed and shaken occasionally. The bottles were kept for twelve hours to attain uniform temperature at 30°. The soluble matter was filtered.

Ion activities were determined by the cation selective resin membrane electrodes. Absence of asymmetry potential was assured during the measurement of e.m.f. The numbers appearing in Table I show good agreement between the predicted values and the values obtained by using resin membrane electrodes for known concentration of soluble Calcium and Barium salts. The saturated solutions of the sparingly soluble salts were used against solution of known activity of the particular cation and from the e.m.f., the cation activities of the salts were calculated assuming anionic activity equal to cationic activity in the case of symmetrical electrolytes.

For very dilute solutions, the e.m.f.s were measured as quickly as possible.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Table I shows the numbers relating the validity of the ion-exchange membrane used in determining the Calcium and Barium ion activities.

TABLE I

Inner Soln. a_1	Outer Soln. a_2	Theo. EMF (mv)	Observed EMF (mv)
0.0081	0.0027	14.2	14.2
0.0027	0.0009	14.2	14.2
0.0009	0.0003	14.2	14.2
0.0003	0.0001	14.2	14.2

The solubility products of the salts except CaSO_4 as shown in the Table II obtained from the literature⁶ agree reasonably well with the values of activity, solubility products realised from the activity measurement by membrane electrodes. In the case of CaSO_4 , the solubility product determined by E.D.T.A. titration under identical condition differs appreciably from the value of the activity solubility product, which demands further detailed study.

6. F. P. Treadwell and W. T. Hall, "Analytical Chemistry", Vol. 1, pages 22—9th English Edition, New York, John Wiley & Sons Inc.

TABLE II

Inner Soln. $a_{Ca^{+2}}$	Outer Soln. Substance	EMF (mv)	(a_+)	$(a_+)^2$	s^2
0.0081	CaSO ₄	-10.0	3.759×10^{-3}	1.39×10^{-5}	2.22×10^{-4}
0.0003	CaCO ₃	14.0	1.024×10^{-4}	1.05×10^{-8}	1.7×10^{-6}
0.0009 $a_{Ba^{+2}}$	CaC ₂ O ₄	34.0	6.625×10^{-5}	3.389×10^{-9}	2.6×10^{-9}
0.0003	BaSO ₄	40.0	1.391×10^{-5}	1.906×10^{-10}	1.2×10^{-10}
0.0027	BaCO ₃	30.0	9×10^{-5}	8.098×10^{-9}	8.1×10^{-9}
0.0027	BaC ₂ O ₄	19.0	6.281×10^{-4}	3.945×10^{-7}	1.7×10^{-7}

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